

EFFECT OF GAMMA RAYS ON YIELD AND YIELD CONTRIBUTING TRAITS OF SESAME (*Sesamum indicum* L.)

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Abstract

Induced mutagenesis is an effective tool for crop improvement and an efficient means to supplement existing germplasm for cultivar improvement in breeding programs. It has been employed successfully to foster additional variability for qualitatively and quantitatively inherited traits in several crop plants. In the present investigation three sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) genotypes GT-10, TKG-22 and Gophya Local were irradiated with different doses of gamma rays viz. 400Gy, 500Gy, 600Gy and 700Gy at Bhabha Atomic Research Centre (BARC), Trombay, Mumbai and were grown along with control at the experimental farm of Dept. of Agril. Botany, Dr.PDKV, Akola to study their effect on various yield and yield contributing traits like days to 50% flowering, days to maturity, plant height, number of branches per plant, number of capsules per plant, length of capsule, number of seeds per capsule, 1000 seed weight (g), and seed yield per plant. In M_1 generation the results revealed that all the characters were significantly reduced compared to the control and there was more reduction at higher doses compared to lower doses for all the characters. The results obtained in the present study indicate that the different doses of gamma rays can be effectively utilized to create variability for various yield and yield contributing traits of sesame.

Keywords: Gamma rays, M_1 generation, Sesame, yield contributing traits, Yield.

Introduction

Sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) is one of the oldest oilseed crops and has been under cultivation in Asia for over 5000 years. In India, the antiquity of sesame is known for the use of its seed in religious ceremonies. The crop is highly tolerant to drought, grows well in most of the well-drained soils and various agro-climatic regions, and is well adapted to different rotations. It can set seed and yield well under fairly high temperatures and can grow in stored soil moisture without rainfall and irrigation (Saxena and Bisen, 2017). However, continuous flooding or severe drought adversely affects the crop resulting in low yield (Mensah *et al.*, 2009).

Sesame oil comprises about 85% unsaturated and 15% saturated fatty acids. The unsaturated fatty acids include linoleic acid (~46%) and oleic acid (~38%), while the saturated fatty acids are palmitic acid (~12%) and stearic acid (~4%). The higher quantity of unsaturated fatty acids present in sesame oil has human health benefits believed to minimize the risks of cardiovascular diseases, cancer, brain, and liver damage. The global annual consumption of sesame is about 65% and 35% in the form of processed food oil and grain respectively. (Teklu *et al.*, 2022).

Most of the crop improvement for yield in sesame is being attempted through conventional breeding methods by exploiting the natural variability available in the germplasm. However, to isolate the most attractive useful genotypes, adequate variability is not available in the existing germplasm. Sesame improvement is still in its infancy and the yield improvement achieved through conventional breeding procedures has been only marginal. Under such circumstances, induced mutagenesis can be efficiently employed as an alternative or supplement source (Brock, 1971) to increase the variability in quantitative traits. Today, the plant breeders have at hand, a number of effective physical and chemical mutagens capable of inducing variation when applied properly. Physical mutagens, especially ionizing radiations have been widely and routinely used to generate genetic variability in various crop species including sesame (Saha and Paul, 2017). Mutation breeding is a potent and handy tool to induce new and additional variability in both the quantitative and qualitative characters. In this context, this study was undertaken to study the effect of gamma rays on quantitative traits to induce the variation in three genotypes viz. GT-10, TKG-22 and Gophya Local.

Material and Methods

The experimental material included in the present study comprised of three varieties of sesame viz., GT-10, TKG-22 and Gophya Local. Dry, uniform, seeds of GT-10, TKG-22 and Gophya Local varieties were irradiated with 400Gy, 500Gy, 600Gy and 700Gy Gamma rays at BARC (Bhabha Atomic Research Centre) Trombay, Mumbai and the same untreated seeds of each variety served as control. The seeds of each treatment were sown in the field during the year 2020 following a Randomized Block Design with five replications along

with control. Row to row and plant to plant distances of 30 cm and 10 cm respectively were maintained. All the recommended agronomic practices and plant protection measures were followed uniformly for all the treatments. This study aims to study the effects of gamma rays on various yield and yield contributing traits in M_1 generation like days to 50% flowering, days to maturity, plant height, number of branches per plant, number of capsules per plant, length of capsule, number of seeds per capsule, 1000 seed weight (g), and seed yield per plant.

Results and Discussion

Significant differences were found for all the studied characters in M_1 generation of all three sesame genotypes (GT-10, TKG-22 and Gophya Local). The mean values for all characters under study are presented in Table 1 for GT-10, Table 2 for TKG-22, and Table 3 for Gophya Local.

In M_1 generation, the maximum days required for 50% flowering was noted in 700 Gy dose in all three genotypes. A delayed flowering for the treatments compared to the control was noticed in all three genotypes. These findings were in agreement with the previous reports of Prabhakar (1985) and Rahman and Das (1989), Ganesan (1995), Govindarasu (1995), Boureima *et al.*, (2009), Saha and Paul (2017c), Rajaramadoss *et al.*, (2014a) and Ravichandran and Jayakumar (2018) in sesame. Gamma rays delayed the days to 50% flowering irrespective of treatment level reported in cowpea by Girija and Dhanavel (2013) and in black gram by Yasmin *et al.* (2016).

Genotypes GT-10, TKG-22 and Gophya Local showed a delay in maturity when treated with all doses of gamma rays as compared to control. The above results were closely related to the findings of Saha and Paul (2017) in sesame.

In M_1 generation reduction in plant height was observed with an increase in doses of gamma rays in all the genotypes namely GT-10, TKG-22 and Gophya Local. Similar results were observed by Boureima *et al.* (2009), RajaRamadoss *et al.* (2014), Anbarasan *et al.* (2015) and Ravichandran and Jayakumar (2018) in sesame, and Girija and Dhanavel (2013) in cowpea. Maximum reduction in plant height was observed at 700Gy of gamma rays as compared to control in all three genotypes. Reduction in plant height may be attributed to chromosomal damage induced during cell division and elongation. Negative shifts in the mean value of plant height following mutagenic treatment have been reported as a gradual phenomenon attributed to the occurrence of deleterious or harmful mutations whose frequency was more than the mutations of desirable nature (Virupakshappa *et al.*, 1980).

The number of branches decreased with an increase in the doses of gamma rays in all three genotypes studied. The highest dose *i.e.* 700Gy of gamma rays was found to be most effective in reducing the number of branches in the genotypes of sesame. The number of branches per plant showed a negative shift in the mean value of

mutagenic treatments. The minimum number of branches per plant was observed at higher doses of gamma rays as compared with the control. Similar observations have been reported with gamma rays by Prabhakar (1985), and Ravichandran and Jayakumar (2018) in sesame for M₁ generation. Reduction in plant height might be due to the toxicity of the mutagens on physiological parameters. Various explanations have been offered for the reduction in the number of branches due to mutagenic treatments like auxin destruction, (Rizwana *et al.*, 2005; Ravichandran *et al.*, 2014), failure of assimilatory mechanisms, inhibition of mitosis and chromosomal damage with associated physiological changes (Saha and Paul, 2017). A negative trend was observed in the number of capsules per plant in M₁ generation. The highest reduction in the number of capsules per plant was observed in 700Gy dose of gamma rays in all three genotypes. RajaRamdoss *et al.* (2014) observed reduction in number of capsules per plant than the control due to the mutagenic treatment of gamma rays in M₁ generation of sesame genotype TTVS-51. The reduction in the number of capsules per plant may be due to the probable inhibitory action of enzymes, changes in the enzyme activity and the toxic effect of the mutagens. A differential response for this character over gamma rays was observed by Anbarasan *et al.* (2015) in sesame.

The gradual reduction in capsule length was observed with increasing gamma radiation doses in all three genotypes studied. The reduced capsule length may be due to physiological and some other disturbances at the genetic level like chromosomal damage disturbed chromosomal coiling, failure or restricted pairing, etc. The gradual reduction in the number of seeds per capsule was observed with increasing gamma radiation doses in all three genotypes. All three capsule characteristics such as the number of capsules per plant, capsule length and seeds per capsule affected in all three genotypes by gamma rays. A dose-dependent reduction in all three capsule characters was noticed. In all the genotypes studied, the highest dose of gamma rays was found to be very effective in significantly reducing the number of capsules per plant, capsule length and seeds per capsule. However, the lowest dose 400Gy showed a low comparable effect to that of the control. Many workers like RajaRamadoss *et al.*, (2014) and Ravichandran and Jayakumar (2018) found a similar effect of mutagens on capsule characters in sesame and also in different crops, such as bhendi (Sasi, 2004) and cluster bean (Velu *et al.*, 2007).

The effect of the highest dose of gamma rays was pronounced in reducing 1000 seed weight than in lower doses which were observed to be comparable. The reduction in 1000 seed weight with an increase in doses of gamma rays in M₁ generation was reported by RajaRamadoss *et al.* (2014), Ariharasutharsan *et al.* (2022) in sesame, Gunasekaran and Padavai (2015) in peanut and Girija and Dhanavel (2013) in cowpea.

All the genotypes under study *viz.* GT-10, TKG-22 and Gophya Local showed a decrease in seed yield per plant with increasing doses of gamma rays. This was in conformity with the observation of Anbarasan *et al.*, (2014), Rajaramadoss *et al.*, (2014), Ravichandran and Jayakumar (2018), and Ariharasutharsana *et al.*, (2022) in sesame. Similar results were recorded in various crops Koteswara Rao *et al.*, (1983) in green gram, and Kalpande *et al.* (2020) in soybean.

The marked reduction caused by mutagens in seed yield per plant can be attributed to high seed sterility as caused by physiological and biochemical disturbances in the development of seeds. (Prabhakaran, 1992). The decline in yield could also be probably due to the indirect influence of altered yield contributing components. (RajaRamdoss *et al.*, 2014).

Conclusions

In the present study, a considerable reduction was observed in all the yield and yield contributing traits of sesame when compared to the control and the yield and yield contributing traits were proportionately decreased with an increase in the dose of gamma rays

in all the three genotypes of sesame. This is due to physiological disturbance or chromosomal damage caused to the cells of plants by gamma rays. The lowest dose of gamma rays showed a low comparable effect to that of the control. While the highest dose of gamma rays significantly reduced the yield and yield contributing characters compared to the control in sesame. Mutagenic treatments increase the genetic variability, which can be utilized for the selection and improvement of sesame plants.

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Table 1: Mean performances of the genotype GT-10 for seed yield and yield contributing characters in M₁ generation

Genotype	Doses	Days to 50% flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	No. branches / plant	No. of capsules / plant	Capsule length (cm)	No. of seeds / capsule	1000 seed weight (g)	Seed yield / plant (g)
GT-10	400Gy	48.00	95.20	91.40	3.30	50.10	2.06	42	2.53	4.30
	500Gy	49.20	96.20	87.80	3.15	44.08	1.95	39	2.46	3.92
	600Gy	51.40	99.00	82.60	2.96	41.20	1.88	37	2.42	3.57
	700Gy	52.20	101.80	79.60	2.68	36.00	1.77	35	2.28	2.28
	Control	44.60	92.00	101.00	4.10	56.48	2.10	48	2.60	4.81
	SE (m)	0.92	1.65	4.34	0.18	2.87	0.06	2.13	0.03	0.24
	CD @ 5%	2.76	4.95	13.00	0.54	8.60	0.19	6.38	0.10	0.73
	C.V. %	4.19	3.81	10.96	12.34	14.07	7.30	11.73	3.09	14.34

Table 2: Mean performances of the genotype TKG-22 for seed yield and yield contributing characters in M₁ generation

Genotype	Doses	Days to 50% flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	No. branches / plant	No. of capsules / plant	Capsule length (cm)	No. of seeds / capsule	1000 seed weight (g)	Seed yield / plant (g)
TKG-22	400Gy	45.40	84.60	89.80	3.68	36.40	2.25	48	2.84	4.90
	500Gy	46.60	86.60	86.40	3.26	33.80	2.08	44	2.69	4.67
	600Gy	47.60	89.60	81.40	2.98	29.40	1.88	39	2.54	4.29
	700Gy	49.80	93.40	71.40	2.42	22.20	1.72	34	2.44	3.43
	Control	42.40	83.20	97.60	3.92	42.36	2.39	53	2.90	5.38
	SE (m)	0.81	1.28	3.89	0.21	1.96	0.06	2.17	0.05	0.33
	CD @ 5%	2.43	3.84	11.66	0.64	5.87	0.18	6.5	0.14	0.99
	C.V. %	3.91	3.27	10.19	14.70	13.33	6.40	11.13	3.89	16.26

Table 3: Mean performances of the genotype Gophya Local for seed yield and yield contributing characters in M₁ generation

Genotype	Doses	Days to 50% flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	No. of capsules / plant	Capsule length (cm)	No. of seeds / capsule	1000 seed weight (g)	Seed yield / plant (g)
Gophya Local	400Gy	52.40	104.60	106.20	38.36	2.24	42.76	2.65	4.47
	500Gy	54.60	105.40	100.80	34.36	2.11	39.64	2.58	4.24
	600Gy	55.80	109.40	96.00	29.04	1.94	35.28	2.47	3.86
	700Gy	59.40	112.00	90.40	21.60	1.78	32.88	2.39	3.24
	Control	50.40	102.20	110.00	41.52	2.31	45.32	2.83	4.93
	SE (m)	1.11	1.48	4.08	1.54	0.07	1.96	0.04	0.28
	CD @ 5%	3.31	4.43	12.24	4.6	0.21	5.87	0.13	0.85
	C.V. %	4.53	3.10	9.07	10.41	7.6	11.17	3.65	15.34